

Data Management Plan I

D1.2 Data Management Plan

WP 1, T 1.5 Data management plan

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Technical references

Project Acronym	DISTENDER
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- * PU = Public
 PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
 RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
 CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

v	Date	Beneficiary	Author
0.0	01/10/2022	UPM	Roberto San José (UPM) and Juan Luis Pérez Camaño (UPM).
0.1	21/10/2022	ICONs, U-GRAZ, UKCEH	Marcello Bardellini (ICONs), Gabriel B-achner (U-GRAZ) and Rob Dunford-Brown (UKCEH),
1.0	01/11/2022	UPM	Roberto San José (UPM) and Juan Luis Pérez Camaño (UPM).

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Abbreviations

CA – Consortium Agreement
 CC – Climate change
 CCS – Core Case Study
 DoA – Description of Action
 DOI -- Document Object Identifier
 DMP – Data Management Plan
 EC – European Commission
 FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
 GA – Grant Agreement
 GDPR – General Data Protection Regulation
 PC – Project Coordinator
 PMP – Project Management Plan
 SC – Steering Committee
 TL – Task Leader
 WP – Work Package
 WPL – Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

This document is the first deliverable of the task 1.5, it is the D1.2 “Data management plan I” of the DISTENDER project. DISTENDER has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101056836. The Data Management Plan (DMP) document provides the overall guidelines and procedures for how the generated data in the project will be organized, stored and shared according to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles and so define the DISTENDER consortium’s data management policy that will be used with regard to the DISTENDER datasets. It specifies which data will be publicly available through public repositories and which will be available only to the consortium (confidential), as far as this is possible, from the project’s initial stage. The present deliverable is the initial version of the DMP to be delivered at Month 6 (M6). The complex structure of the project, the heterogeneity of climate projects, and the complexity of the workplan will require frequent updates of the DMP that will be consolidated in the deliverables D1.3 M36, it will go into more detail regarding the datasets produces by the DISTENDER project.

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1 Project summary

DISTENDER will provide integrated strategies by building a methodological framework that guides the integration of climate change (CC) adaptation and mitigation strategies through participatory approaches in ways that respond to the impacts and risks of climate change (CC), supported by quantitative and qualitative analysis that facilitates the understanding of interactions, synergies and trade-offs. Holistic approaches to mitigation and adaptation must be tailored to the context-specific situation and this requires a flexible and participatory planning process to ensure legitimate and salient action, carried out by all important stakeholders. DISTENDER will develop a set of multi-driver qualitative and quantitative socio-economic-climate scenarios through a facilitated participatory process that integrates bottom-up knowledge and locally-relevant drivers with top-down information from the global European Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) and downscaled Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) from IPCC. A cross-sectorial and multi-scale impact assessment modelling toolkit will be developed to analyse the complex interactions over multiple sectors, including an economic evaluation framework. The economic impact of the different efforts will be analysed, including damage claim settlement and how sectoral activity patterns change under various scenarios considering indirect and cascading effects. DISTENDER is an innovative project combining three key concepts: cross-scale, integration/harmonization and robustness checking. DISTENDER will follow a pragmatic approach applying methodologies and toolkits across a range of European case studies (five core case studies and six followers) that reflect a cross-section of the challenges posed by CC adaptation and mitigation. The knowledge generated by DISTENDER will be offered by a Decision Support System (DSS).

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2 Introduction

A Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines how data are to be handled both during a research project, and after a project is completed. The goal of a DMP is to consider the many aspects of data management, metadata generation, data preservation and analysis, which ensures that data are well-managed in the present, and prepared for preservation in the future.

The development and management of the DMP along the project duration, is part of WP1 – “Project Management”. The Data Management Plan, although part of the of WP1 activities, has connections with all WPs that collect and/or generate data. This deliverable is closely related to the deliverable D12.1 “Ethics requirements No. 1” which establishes the measures and protocols that are taken to safeguard and protect sensitive data. This report also summarises the intermediate results of the data requirements activities in the task 9.2

The primary audience to which this report is addressed are the 31 internal partnerships., Since the beginning of the project the DMP supports partners in considering all the relevant aspects of data management, by establishing consistent practices among partners to increase the efficiency and robustness of data handling along the course of the project. Another audience of the DMP is the community of researchers, engineers, practitioners, city planners, policy makers, interested in re-using datasets produced by DISTENDER.

DISTENDER maximizes the access to and re-use of research data generated by the project. The data will be of interest to other researchers, public administrations, service operators and other stakeholders. The data generated in the project will be available in a research data repository so that it will be possible to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate it, free of charge for any user. Also, the DISTENDER methodology will be made available so other can reproduce it.

Open results (deliverables and research data) of the DISTENDER will be published in Zenodo. Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository much used for publishing deliverables and data of H2020 and Horizon projects. Zenodo exports the data to OpenAIRE, a network of Open Access repositories to support the EC publication policies. Resources in Zenodo (consequently also in OpenAire) are identified with a Document Object Identifier (DOI), they can be versioned. With Zenodo long term preservation of data is very likely. Moreover, common search engines such as Google Scholar or Microsoft Research are aware of the assets hosted at Zenodo and they enjoy high visibility. The Zenodo DISTENDER community will be linked to the project website facilitating provision/access to the different types of documents/databases.

The Project Coordination is responsible for monitoring the compliance with the proposed regulations, keep the DMP updated, and promote actions of prevention, detection and response to possible incidents related to the confidentiality of the information and data managed, although it may be delegated to some partners for specific cases.

For internal documents such as working papers, minutes of meeting, agendas and draft version of the deliverables a SharePoint (SHP) platform has been setup as the internal repository of the DISTENDER project. The storage space is located at the UPM (Madrid, Spain). A description and guide how to use the SHP has been distributed to all partners and is contained in ANNEX I. SHP eases the collaboration and increases transparency among the various consortium partners to locate and access the project documentation.

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During the project's lifetime, a significant amount of collected and generated data needs to be exchanged among the partners of the consortium. **To share data (no documents) between DISTENDER partners, a Secure File Transfer Protocol (SFTP) server has been established (ambiente.lma.fi.upm.es) on UPM servers** (coordinator), where all the project data will be stored. A description and guide how to use the SFTP has been distributed to all partners and is contained in ANNEX II.

The DISTENDER data flow is described in the Figure 1

Figure 1: Data flow of the DISTENDER project.

3 Data summary

The development of integrated adaptation and mitigation strategies for the CC will require the collection, processing and storage of a large variety of data sets such as environmental and meteorological data, socio-economic data, geographic data, etc. The identification of the specific data sets is now part of the work of T9.2 “Data requirements”, so in this initial version of the DMP a more general overview of the type of datasets is given.

DISTENDER WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8 will make use of different and heterogeneous external and internal sources of data. In order to achieve their goals, the data requirements have been analysed in T9.2 “Data requirements” and the input and output datasets will be described in detail in the Deliverable D9.2 “Data for case studies” in M12. Beyond the above-mentioned types of data, WP11 will collect and treat specific personal data as described by the Privacy Notice published on the DISTENDER website

3.1 Inputs from external sources

The identified data to be collected in the first phase of the project comprise a variety of climate, environmental, geographical and morphological datasets, as well as demographic and socio-economic datasets, which are primarily needed for modelling climate impacts and risks, vulnerability and cost-benefit assessments in the DISTENDER CCS, which are very relevant for the co-development of the adaptation and mitigation strategies. Part of these data sets will be provided by the CCS and also existing datasets will be downloaded from European services as EEA Urban Atlas, Copernicus Land Monitoring Services, and CMIP6 numerical global climate simulations. All these datasets will be used as input for the high resolution climate, environmental, impacts, economic models of the WP4, WP5, WP7. A more specific list of the inputs is described in the following list.

- **Global climate model outputs:** Climate scenarios from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) global climate models (GCMs), whose results were used in the latest Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Assessment Report (AR6), will be used to downscale the global climate scenario to local climate scenarios in WP4. The complete archive of CMIP6 output is made available for search and download via the following portals:
 - o USA, PCMDI/LLNL (California) - <https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/cmip6/>
 - o France, IPSL - <https://esgf-node.ipsl.upmc.fr/search/cmip6-ipsl/>
 - o Germany, DKRZ - <https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/search/cmip6-dkrz/>
 - o UK, CEDA - <https://esgf-index1.ceda.ac.uk/search/cmip6-ceda/>

In this case we are talking about large amounts of data as it is global data, therefore each partner will download the data it needs and will keep it stored locally without sharing it with other partners or publicly unless it receives a specific request for a set of data, in which case the data stored in the SFTP will be made available to the requesting partner.

- **Observational data** from core case studies: For each CCS data from air quality, meteorological and hydrological networks will be collected. Typically, this are in situ measurements in the form of time series. Such data will be used in the project

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according to the policy of the data providers that usually do not include the possibility of sharing data outside the consortium.

- **High resolution geographic** data sets: Geographic data are geo-referenced data of the geographic domain of the case study. They are data that can be read by Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and must be provided in files that can be read by a GIS. Data can be raster, vector or point data.
- **Socio-Economic** data sets: Data sets describing the socio-economic situation of the CCS.
 - o The macroeconomic CGE model will be calibrated to data from the IIASA SSP database - <https://tntcat.iiasa.ac.at/SspDb/>
 - o Indicator datasets (e.g. demographic information) illustrating baseline information/statistics associated with the case studies. These may include spatial datasets or local/national aggregated data depending on the indicator in question.
 - o Modelled future projections (e.g. of population, GDP) from existing studies such as the IIASA SSP database (above).

3.2 Outputs from WPs

- **WP3** will produce local socio-economic scenarios through co-creation processes and starting from the global Shared Socio-Economic scenarios. The data will be geographic data, population and other indicators to describe the future evolution of the CCS up to 2050.
- **WP4** will produce high resolution climate scenarios for the CCS after running dynamical and statistical downscaling models/tools.
- **WP5** will produce high resolution climate change impacts runs with inputs from WP4 datasets for different sectors: air quality, urban heat island, health, water, agroforestry to perform a vulnerability assessment in each case study. Economic evaluation will be developed in WP7.
- **WP6** will co-develop adaptation and mitigation strategies for the six CCS based on climate impacts assessed in WP5 and economic models of WP7. WP6 will not produce large amounts of data itself but by working closely with other WPs will determine inputs that influence the drivers of the third run of WP4/5 models.
- **WP7** will quantify sectoral and economy-wide economic effects of climate change impacts, mitigation and adaptation. Sectoral economic assessments will be done for water, agroforestry, health (via heat and air quality) as well as energy. WP7 will translate bio-physical impacts from WP5 into economic dimensions.
- **WP8** will integrate the outputs from the WP6 to develop a multicriteria decision system to help policymakers analyse the different climate strategies from different points of views: environmental, social, economic

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The partners (or the partner) that have contributed to each product will be considered as shared owners of the products.

For Communication and Dissemination purposes, in the context of WP11 activities, the following will apply:

- **Data collected:**
 - Names and email addresses (e.g., subscribers to the newsletter)
 - Analytics from project's website and social media platforms (Twitter and LinkedIn), Matomo, and social monitoring tool Nuvi©
- **Type of data:**
 - Data used to support D&C activities
 - Data used to analyse outreach and impact of D&C activities
- **Type of datasets generated:**
 - List of registered users
 - Dataset of D&C indicators
- **Data sources/ collection methods:**
 - Registration on the project's landing page & website, direct contacts
 - Wordpress, Matomo, social media analytics, Nuvi©
- **Origin of data:**
 - Individual subscription to the C&D current or former C&D activities;
 - Project's D&C platforms
- **Data process:**
 - C&D activities such as NL e-mailing, events
 - Quantitative methods
- **Purpose:**
 - D&C activities
 - Monitoring of D&C impacts; analysis of outreach and engagement; creation of D&C indexes (e.g., ICONS PEI, WEI, SEI, CEI, etc.)
- **Data sharing:**

The data collected are not shared but only used directly by ICONS for the abovementioned activities.

- Data used to support D&C activities – confidential.
- Data used to analyse the impacts of D&C activities – Final aggregated data (D&C indicators and indexes) can be shown publicly.
- **Standards/Metadata:**

Standard metadata provided by the processing tools which will be used (e.g., Matomo and social media analytics)

3.3 Data formats

The different data sets could have different formats, the different initial formats used are summarized in Table 1. These formats are shown in an illustrative way as they are the ones that have been identified in this initial phase of the project, the table could be extended depending on the needs of the project and the complete table will be reported in the final version of the Data Management deliverable.

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Table 1 Summary of the DISTENDER data format

Type of data	Formats
Numerical or textual tabular data	Comma-separated values (.csv) or Microsoft Excel (.xls/.xlsx)
Qualitative textual data	ASCII text (.text) , Microsoft Word (.doc/.docx) or Portable document format (.pdf)
Raster/Gridded data	Netcdf, Hdf, Geotiff
Vector	ESRI shapefile, DBF, KML
Images	Png, jpg

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4 Scientific publications

DISTENDER research partners must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results as described in the article 17 “COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, OPEN SCIENCE AND VISIBILITY (— ARTICLE 17)” of the GA. They will publish project results in **Open Access Journals**. Open access can be defined as the practice of providing on-line access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and that is re-usable. To meet this requirement, beneficiaries will ensure that the publications can be read online, downloaded and printed (free of charge, online access to any user).

The open access to publications procedure will comprise 3 steps:

1. Selecting the open access route
2. Providing open access to publications
3. Depositing the data in repositories (online archive) in order to allow for replicability of the results.

The most traditional ways to achieve open access are the Green and Gold routes. The Green route, or self-archiving route, is based on the practice of depositing previously published articles in an open access repository. The repository can be institutional and/or general (e.g. Zenodo). A publication can be deposited in more than one repository. The Gold route consists of the editor of a journal publishing the articles in open access immediately and permanently, under a license where the author maintains the copyright. Journals usually require a payment for publication costs, the so-called APCs (article processing charges). **DISTENDER has adopted the green route as the most appropriate path to publish its results.** Only in exceptional cases the possibility of publishing in a golden journal will be considered, for which interested partners must apply to the coordinator for advance approval.

Before submitting a publication, partners have to follow paragraph 8.4.2.1 Publication of the CA: *“Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before submission of the publication.”*

Informative presentations (without publications) at conferences, workshops or symposiums, do not require to follow the 8.4.2.1 rule as they mainly inform only on DISTENDER (mainly by the Coordinator), but they should be reported an advance.

A registry of the scientific publications and dissemination events of the project will be stored in the SHP area (WP11 folder), this repository will be maintained and updated by ICONS (leader of the WP11 “Communication, dissemination and exploitation”) with the support of the UPM as coordinator. All partners will inform ICONS by email with copy to the coordinator (UPM) of any communication and dissemination event or publication related to DISTENDER project results, to be stored in the dissemination activities register. The information of the register will be used for the periodic reports to the EU commission.

5 FAIR data

This DMP describes the data management procedures that are followed according to the FAIR principles. The acronym FAIR identifies the main features that the project research data must have in order to be *findable, accessible, interoperable and re-useable*, allowing thus for maximum knowledge circulation.

5.1 Findable

In order to make data findable, the main tool has to assure that data used and produced in the project can be discovered through metadata. An internal guide on how to generate the metadata of the DISTENDER results will be prepared and circulated to all the DISTENDER partners.

Datasets will be described using a **metadata standard** in order to ensure metadata interoperability for indexing and discoverability following the convention of the hosting research data repository. There are many different meta-data standards for many different types of data and it may not be possible to find one that fits all purposes. Therefore, a pragmatic and feasible approach is to agree on a common and minimal catalogue metadata schema for those datasets that are published in public catalogues and data repositories and to use data-type specific schema extensions, if necessary. In general, the Zenodo deposition metadata domain model which is based on DataCite's metadata schema's minimum and recommended terms will be used for open data generated by the project and deposited in an appropriate repository.

For DISTENDER, the following deposition metadata fields are mandatory:

- **title:** Title of the deposition.
- **description:** Abstract or description for deposition.
- **files:** Deposition files identifiers, filenames, size of the files in bytes and MD5 checksum of files
- **upload_type:** Type of the deposition from a controlled vocabulary (publication, dataset, software, ...).
- **publication_date:** Date of publication in ISO8601 format (YYYY-MM-DD).
- **creators:** The creators/authors of the deposition.
- **license** Open license from controlled vocabulary "Open Definition Licenses Service"
- **doi:** Digital Object Identifier assigned by the DOI registrant (e.g. Zenodo),
- **keywords:** Free forms word to identify the datasets.
- **related_identifiers:** Persistent identifiers of related publications, datasets and software
- **communities** List of communities where the data is deposited. (<https://zenodo.org/communities/distender/>)
- **grants:** European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101056836.

Open DISTENDER results will be assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) in order to make content easily and uniquely citable. Valid and machine readable DOIs allow other

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repositories to find and identify the datasets deposited by DISTENDER. Moreover, all partners are strongly recommended to make use of DOI to make datasets produced by DISTENDER citable.

The DISTENDER data file names will follow common rules in order to improve data visibility, discoverability, citation and permanent online tracking. The name of files will be:

DISTENDER_WP?_TitleSpecifyingDatasetContent_VersionNumber_PublicationDate.extension

Example: DISTENDER_WP4_AirtemperatureSSP485Austria20142050_v1.0_22092022.nc

5.2 Accessible

According to the principle expressed as "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" restrictions on data access or sharing will be considered only in the following cases:

- when collected data belongs to third party which have denied permission for sharing them on account of confidentiality and proprietary issues;
- protection of personal data of key informants involved in surveys, focus groups, interviews, and case studies as drafted in DISTENDER D12.1 "Ethics" deliverable;
- stakeholders of the CCS do not give permission to disclose some results (sensitive information),

Sensitive data provided by consortium partners for the CCS and personal data of the stakeholders will be kept strictly confidential and anonymized, but all the other data sets will be accessible in Zenodo open repository.

At the time of presentation of results in scientific peer-reviewed publications, researchers will deposit the project data that can be shared in a data repository, to guarantee their accessibility and preservation beyond the project. Zenodo is the recommended platform for open dissemination and preservation of research data by all research teams that do not have suitable institutional, national, or disciplinary data repositories or are not bound to use their institutional repositories.

As a guiding principle, DISTENDER seeks to make research data openly available, whenever possible, to allow for dissemination and validation, and to increase the re-use potential of research results. To this purpose, all the files will be converted to standard and well-documented open formats and the datasets that will be deposited will include all relevant documentation and explanation. Considering formats listed in Table 1, there will be no need to use specifically tailored software to access project datasets, since they are open format and there is free software available to work with the datasets.

5.3 Interoperable

Making data interoperable allows for data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. The main goal is to facilitate the re-combination of the data from different sources. For that, the use of standard formats and of available (open) software applications is promoted.

To allow data exchange and re-use among researchers, institutions, organizations, countries, etc., partners will convert all shareable data from proprietary formats and make

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them available in well-known and documented, possibly open, formats (see Table 1 for details), as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications.

5.4 Re-usable

DISTENDER is committed to permit the widest use of collected/generated data that will be shareable by distributing them and by adopting licenses that allow their re-use by other researchers and stakeholders. It is envisaged that datasets will be made available mainly under Creative Commons license CC BY 4.0 and Open Data Commons ODC-BY2.0. The first gives permission to users to freely share, modify, and use the data, subject only to full credit to the author(s) of the dataset. Note that ODC-BY is a license specifically drafted for Open Data projects that works under condition of compatibility with Open Access requirements, interoperability, and re-use. The CC BY NC 4.021, requiring full credit but limiting the re-use for commercial purposes, can be chosen instead in case of data collected from sources that pose limits to re-use.

DISTENDER data will be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible, when no limitations are identified by the CCS stakeholders.

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6 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

During DISTENDER, internal storage systems have been set up and adopted to share data and documents among partners. UPM is responsible of these platforms. The cost to activate and maintain the storage systems for the duration of the project and two years beyond its end will be covered by the WP1 project budget (UPM partner budget). The partners producing data are responsible to implement the DMP. Making data FAIR requires a certain amount of researchers' time, the cost of each partner is covered by their budgets. The open data of the project will be published in Zenodo where there are accessible at no costs for long term deposit and preservation of public shareable data because Zenodo does not apply fees for archiving data and data curation.

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7 DATA SECURITY

During the project, relevant research data will be managed through the SHP and SFTP platforms. They are subject to regular backup to safeguard from accidental data losses and protected using links and password mechanisms described in the Annex I and Annex II.

Long term preservation of public data is ensured by the chosen data repositories that have specific preservation policies. For example, Zenodo policy ensures that the items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository and in case of closure, best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

At each institution, research data will be stored in computers, laptops, intranets or hard-drives accessible through passwords periodically modified according to national provisions for data security and protected by regularly updated firewalls & antiviruses. All the data will be password protected. All Partners are asked to keep locally updated copies of all their files. All research materials stored in computers will be subject to regular backup in order to safeguard them from accidental losses.

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8 ETHICS AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

All ethics requirements of the DISTENDER project are reflected in the D12.1 “Ethics requirements No. 1 in the WP12. It defines how to take into account several aspects, such as details on what type of personal data will be collected; details on data transference to non-EU countries and human participation. DISTENDER will observe applicable national and EU legislation concerning data collection and privacy, in particular, EU’s General Data Protection Regulation 679/2016 (GDPR) as described in more detail in D12.1

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ANNEX I DISTENDER SHAREPOINT (SHP)

In order to facilitate the exchange of documentation between partners and to ensure that all partners have access to the project documents, a document sharing area has been established, which will be called **DISTENDER SharePoint Area (DSPA)**. It is based on the Microsoft 365 SharePoint application (you can obtain more information on [Get-started-with-sharepoint](#)). **You can use it without having a Microsoft account. Access control to documentation is done via e-mail.**

You will receive an email as follows:

The link to access (read mode without edit permissions) the DSPA: DISTENDER.

The partners will only be able to log in with the e-mail address which is used as contact person in the contact person list we are currently using for the coordination communications. As a security measure, the system will initiate a verification procedure by sending you a code to your email address (DISTENDER contact person e-mail) (see next picture):

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Microsoft

Enter Verification Code

You've received a secure link to:

 DISTENDER

To open this link, enter the code we just emailed to jupelma@hotmail.es. [Send again](#)

Enter code

Verify

Keep me signed in

© 2017 Microsoft Privacy & Cookies

Check your email for the code, enter the code on the provided form and click on the “Verify” button. This is the interface to explore the folders and documents (it communicates in different languages, English is the default):

The screenshot shows a SharePoint site for the 'DISTENDER HORIZON EU PROJECT'. The page title is 'POLITÉCNICA Office 365'. The site is a private group with 2 members. The main content area displays a list of documents under the heading 'Documents > DISTENDER'. The list has columns for Name, Modified, and Modified By. All documents are folders named WP1 through WP9, all modified 5 days ago by JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO.

Name	Modified	Modified By
WP1	5 days ago	JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO
WP10	5 days ago	JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO
WP11	5 days ago	JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO
WP12	5 days ago	JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO
WP2	5 days ago	JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO
WP3	5 days ago	JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO
WP4	5 days ago	JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO
WP5	5 days ago	JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO
WP6	5 days ago	JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO
WP7	5 days ago	JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO
WP8	5 days ago	JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO
WP9	5 days ago	JUAN LUIS PEREZ CAMAÑO

By default, all partners (contact e-mail address) have **READING PERMISSION (not edit or delete)** and will therefore **have access to all folders and documents**. **Work Package leaders** have additional permissions to edit/upload documents and to allow writing permissions to other partners in his/her WP in their folders. These are the links to be used by the WP leaders (the general [DISTENDER](#) link is **only to read the documents**) to access with editing permissions:

[WP1](#) [WP2](#) [WP3](#) [WP4](#) [WP5](#) [WP6](#) [WP7](#) [WP8](#) [WP9](#) [WP10](#) [WP11](#) [WP12](#)
[OFFICIAL MEETINGS](#) This link is for documents (no videos) of the meetings. All contact partners have editing permissions.

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DISTENDER

ANNEX II DISTENDER SFTP SERVER (SFTP)

A Secure File Transfer Protocol (SFTP) Data Server is hosted by UPM to store large amounts of data, mainly for the modelling tasks and case studies data, with special security capabilities to protect all sensitive data. This server will keep all Core Case Study data such as GIS data, meteorology data, air pollution data, etc. and outputs from modelling tasks. The SFTP Data Server will allow to upload or download high volumes of data.

Server login information

Hostname: ambiente.lma.fi.upm.es

Port: 2212

Username: distender_data

Password: It will be send in a separate e-mail for security reason.

The easy way for Connecting to the SFTP Data Server is using a client. An SFTP client is a software which uses the SFTP protocol to transfer files securely to and from a remote computer. You can use one of the most used Free SFTP Clients: **WinSCP** (<https://winscp.net/eng/download.php>) or **FileZilla®** (<https://filezilla-project.org/download.php?platform=win64>) which is available for Windows, Linux, Mac. After to installing the SFTP client, follow the corresponding connexion figure to the SFTP Data Server. **Be carefully that the port number is not a standard number, it is 2212** for security reasons. After de connexion is established you can copy data from/to your computer to/from DISTENDER data server

WinSCP

The screenshot shows the WinSCP 'Session' dialog box. It is a standard Windows-style window with a title bar containing minimize, maximize, and close buttons. The main area is titled 'Session' and contains several input fields: 'File protocol:' with 'SFTP' entered; 'Host name:' with 'ambiente.lma.fi.upm.es' entered; 'Port number:' with '2212' entered; 'User name:' with 'distender_data' entered; and 'Password:' which is masked with a series of black dots. Below these fields are two buttons: 'Edit' and 'Advanced...'. At the bottom of the dialog, there are three buttons: 'Login' (with a green plus icon), 'Close', and 'Help'.

[Data Management Plan I]

FileZilla®

In WinSCP:

1. When you fill in all required data, including the password (sent separately in a different e-mail), you can save all the information for further connections to avoid to fill in all the information everytime to entry.
2. Please note that after the connection is establish, on your right side you have to enter the DISTENDER folder to start to transfer data files. Simply click on the DISTENDER folder.
3. Please note that when the connection is established, your computer will be on the LEFT and the FTP data server in UPM will be on your RIGHT in the screen. You can simply click on the file you wish to move from your local data and drag it to your right area inside the DISTENDER data server in UPM.

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